

THE ODDITY OF THE SATURNIAN SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

On the basis of Cassini images and of some diagrams a few provocative questions are raised in connection with the Saturnian System as a whole, namely the origin and evolution of the Saturnian ice-ring system, as well as that of Hyperion and Iapetus. (The recognitions of the author are italicized.)

THE SATURNIAN SATELLITE SYSTEM

Fig. 1. diagram demonstrates the oddity of the Saturnian system as a whole, as compared to that of Jupiter. Was it possible *that the original regular satellite system of Saturn might have been broken into fragments?*

Fig. 1 Distances of the regular satellites from the four giant planets are plotted in units of their own planetary radius. The resonant positions between the satellites are marked by arcs.

Fig. 2 The densities (a), the eccentricities (b) and the inclinations (c) of the larger satellites of the Solar System are plotted in order of increasing inclinations respectively.

Jupiter and Saturn have giant moons, Jupiter four (Galilean moons), Saturn one (Titan). *If around Saturn, in the distance of Titan, there was so many material in the circum-saturnian ring that a moon (Titan) as big as Ganymede could have originated, it is difficult to understand why*

Saturn does not also has more giant moons nearer than Titan. Or Saturn also had more giant moons in its original regular satellite system, only something has happened with them? Is it possible, for example, that when migrating Jupiter and Saturn reached the 1:2 resonance (Nice model, Tsiganis et. al., 2005), then not only the planetesimal-disc has been scattered, but at the same time the original regular satellite system of Saturn has also been taken apart (see also results of Bell,S.W., 2020).

THE MOST PECULIAR OBJECTS IN THE SATURNIAN SYSTEM

Iapetus

Iapetus is one of the most interesting and enigmatic bodies in the Solar System with its quasi-hemispheric differences as regards its surface albedo (Fig 3, 4, 5, 6) and with a long and high equatorial ridge along the equator (Fig 5).

The albedo difference

Since the bright trailing hemisphere has about the same albedo as that of the other satellites of Saturn, it was supposed that the dark leading hemisphere is the one, which needs explanation. Up-till-now three main types of mechanisms have been suggested to explain the presence of the dark material.

External source: the dust left behind by the moon Phoebe served as an external source. The dark dust might have been swept up by the locked Iapetus. The difference in color between Phoebe and the dark material of Iapetus has been explained by impact induced chemical alterations of the surface-material of Iapetus, caused by the large impact velocity of the dust particles originating from the retrograde Phoebe. The discovery of the Phoebe-ring strengthened this hypothesis, as well as *the fact that the Cassini images (Fig. 3) demonstrate that the boundary of the dark material is not parallel with the orbit of Iapetus, but with the equatorial plane of Saturn* – as it would be expected from an outside source e.g. a Saturnian moon. It is, however, *disturbing for me that the Phoebe-dust obviously does not create strong hemispheric differences on the other Saturnian satellites, as in the case of Iapetus.*

Fig. 3 Iapetus with polar caps.

The Cassini images, however, demonstrate (Fig. 3, 4) that the *dark material is not filling up the whole cross section*, as expected in the case of an outside origin. The inadequacy in the direction of North-South has been explained by polar caps, and – as Iapetus does not have an atmosphere – random walk of sublimated water ice molecules was suggested as the mechanism for the origin of polar caps.

The explanation of the East-West inadequacy of the cross section is still missing. On the Cassini images it is very conspicuous that around the equator the albedo border between the bright and dark sides is irregularly shaped (Fig. 4), and moreover, spotted by very sharp boundaries of the spots that refer to sublimation processes (Fig. 6). *Albeit in a smooth stream of dust coming from Phoebe a continuous decrease of the darkness would be expected.*

Endogenous source has been suggested, as volcanic flooding. Earth-based radar observations from Arecibo at 12.6 cm (Black, 2004) and Cassini measurements at 2.2 cm demonstrated that the albedo of the two sides of Iapetus do not differ from each other in these wavelengths: i.e. a very fine, thin surface layer is lying on the material underneath. High resolution Cassini images show a *transparent boundary of the dark material in the north direction* (Fig 5). Both kinds of observations rule out a thick volcanic flooding.

The large equatorial ridge on Iapetus

A linear ridge of at least 1300 km long, 13 km high and 20 km broad can be seen on the leading side of Iapetus (Fig.5), running along 75% of the whole equator. Its existence was explained 1.) by the despin of Iapetus, or 2.) by raining down of particles of an ancient ring of debris that might originate as a consequence of a huge impact into Iapetus.

Fig. 4 The trailing side of Iapetus

Fig. 5 The leading side of Iapetus with the equatorial ridge

Fig. 6 The albedo pattern between the bright and dark side of Iapetus

The problem with both explanations is, however, that the *ridge is not completely circumferential*, although both models demand that it should run along the whole equator. Either *it is necessary to explain why a part of the ridge disappeared, or to find another explanation for the formation of an incomplete ridge.*

For this second version a more suitable source of debris could emerge after a collision in the vicinity of Iapetus between another (captured?) saturnian moon and another large body. A part of the debris left behind by that collision would produce a ring around Saturn. Transiting the nodes the debris could be swept up gradually only by the leading side of Iapetus forming the equatorial ridge.

The orbital inclination of Iapetus

The position (Fig. 1) and the large orbital inclination (Fig. 2.c) of Iapetus is unique among the regular satellites of the Solar System. On the one hand a question is raised *what happened with Iapetus?* On the other hand the *consequence of a significant inclination of a satellite can be tidal heating, if the rotational axis of the satellite is not perpendicular to its orbital plane. If the upwelling plume of the mantle flow occurs on the bright hemisphere, it might cause there a thinner crust, where the ridge could have been relaxed and disappeared.*

Hyperion

Because of its orbital elements, it has never been questioned in the literature that Hyperion was a regular moon of Saturn. The only strange thing in connection with it is that it does not rotate locked, like all the other regular moons in the Solar System; moreover, it rotates in a chaotic manner. These observational facts were explained by a possible collision in the not too distant past.

Fig. 7 Phoebe

Fig. 8 Hyperion

Fig. 9 Mimas

Fig.2a, 2b, 2c diagrams display for the larger satellites of the Solar System the density, the orbital eccentricity and the orbital inclination in order of increasing inclination respectively. But looking at Hyperion's position at the diagrams in Fig.2.a and 2.b, as well as its spongy appearance (Fig.8) reveal that *Hyperion does not look a normal, solid, regular icy moon*, like Mimas (Fig.9). With its deep impact-craters it seems to have very loose structure. It has rather some similarity to Phoebe (Fig.7) which, on the basis of its peculiar orbit, has been considered already very early a captured cometary nucleus in the literature.

Its strange appearance and its low density (Fig.2.a) unambiguously suggest that *Hyperion is a captured KBO. Its capture has to be happened relatively not long time ago, because of its fresh, not eroded appearance and of its chaotic rotation.*

Saturn's two ring-systems

Comparing the rings of the four giant planets (Fig. 10) it is evident that the ring-system of Saturn is very peculiar with its broad and bright stripe. The other three giant planets have only dark, narrow and thin ring-systems.

The Galileo probe proved at Jupiter that the dark dust rings are created by micrometeoroid bombardment onto the small, inner moons. The dusting of the different satellites gives rise to the different components of the dark dust rings. Probably the process is the same at the other giant planets including Saturn.

Nevertheless, according to early radar (Goldstein and Morris, 1973, Goldstein and Green, 1977 and Cuzzi et al. 1978) as well as recent Cassini measurements, the Saturnian bright ring is mostly from water ice. The particles are of cm magnitude, only a few are larger. They do not take their origin by condensation from the Saturnian nebula, but rather by fragmentation.

After the evaluation of the Cassini spectroscopic results it has been suggested that the fragmentation of a saturnian icy moon had been the source of the icy ring. *If, however, the origin of an icy ring would be a common one, then some other giant planets should have to possess bright rings as well. As this is not the case, so with Saturn a peculiar single event had to have happened!*

So I prefer the hypothesis of L. Dones (1991), who has suggested that a Chiron-like giant cometary nucleus (a KBO) has been captured by Saturn and disintegrated inside its Roche limit,

supplying the material of the icy ring. *In that case, however, Saturn has two independent ring-systems of different origin in the same place.*

Fig. 10 The ring systems of the four giant planets

Recently Cassini with its high spacial resolution measurements demonstrated that in the C ring there is mainly low albedo dust, in the B ring there is mainly pure water ice, while in the A ring there is dirty water ice (Fig. 11, lower line, right).

The two ring-systems occupy roughly the same place and both of them suffer from the moons as divisions are formed by them in both ring systems. Their small particles move inward because of the Poynting Robertson effect. Interaction occurs, however, between the two kinds of ring systems: the dust particles make the ice particles dirty, if they collide – especially often near the birthplace of the low albedo dust particles. That is why the “A” part of the ice-ring is more dirty than the “B” part of ring, because near the A ring there are a lot of dust-ejecting moons.

The low albedo dust rings are stationary by dynamical equilibrium because the many moons give continuously the dust-supply. The dust particles themselves always disappear in a timescale of 10^8 years from the ring because of the Poynting Robertson effect, but the low albedo dust-ring system is supplied and maintained continuously by the newly knocked out dust particles – similarly to the other giant planets.

The ice-ring system is temporary in that sense, that if the material of the giant comet exhausted, there will be no supply. So the capture event has to be happened in the not too distant past.

In what distance from Saturn the ice-ring started to form?

I suggest that the disintegration of the giant comet occurred at that distance from the planet, where the B ring is the brightest on the lit side (Fig. 11, upper row, left), and is the darkest and coldest on the unlit side (Fig. 11 upper row, right).

The disintegration is probably continuing even now. This is demonstrated 1.) by the non-uniform brightness of the “B+A” ring, 2.) by the non-uniform opacity of the “B+A” ring that is the particles are still too near to each other in the middle of the B ring, where the sunlight can not

pass through the ring (that can be the reason why the B ring is so cold there), 3.) by the non-uniform dirtiness (that is the “B+A” ring is not uniformly dirty: the low albedo dust particles had still not enough time to penetrate everywhere), 4.) by the fact that in the C ring there are mainly

Fig. 11 Saturnian ring (Cassini images and measurements). Upper line: lit side (left), unlit side (right), lower line: temperature at the unlit side (left), composition (right).

low albedo dust particles (either the micrometeoroid bombardment had still not enough time to pulverize the icy chunks and/or the ice-pulver had still not enough time to reach the C ring .

The ring at that distance, where the disintegration is continuing, can still be „many-particles thick” – in contrast with the edges where it can behave as a monolayer. So it may be that a single model can not describe the whole ring neither in composition nor in layer type.

Can be some connection between the parent body of the icy-ring and the progenitor of Hyperion? Very probably, the capture of a KBO is not a frequent event. So we do not need to suppose that at Saturn already two independent events occurred, but it is not impossible that the primary cometary nucleus of Hyperion splitted: a piece of it was captured into Hyperion’s present orbit, another piece was captured inside the Roche limit, where it was fragmented into the ice-ring. If this would be the case then Hyperion has to be very young in the present orbit – as the lifetime of an icy ring is quite limited.

CONCLUSIONS

Iapetus: The large orbital inclination of Iapetus could have been given rise to tidal heating that offers a possibility for mantle circulation and, as a consequence, for different thickness of its crust.

Hyperion: Hyperion might be a captured giant cometary nucleus (KBO).

Ice-ring: Saturn has two ring-systems of independent origin partly occupying the same place, evolving independently, but interacting with each other: the dust-ring system and the ice-ring system (the “B+A” ring). The low albedo dust rings come continuously into existence similarly as those at other giant planets (by the dust loss of their inner moons). The “B+A” ice-ring system might take its origin by tidal fragmentation of a captured giant cometary nucleus (a part of which, the moon Hyperion, may orbiting around Saturn now). The low albedo dust-ring system is stationary by dynamical equilibrium, the ice-ring system is temporary, as it is the consequence of a rare peculiar event. The disintegration and the spreading of the ice-ring system can continue even now. The fragmentation started at the very distance from Saturn where the B ring is the brightest on the lit side, darkest and coldest on the unlit side. In the vicinity of that place the ice-ring can be many-particle-thick in contrast to the edges, where it can behave as a monolayer. Therefore, it is supposed that a single model can not describe the Saturnian ring system, neither in composition nor in layer structure.

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